

Summary of the study's material:

Overcoming Obstacles: challenges of gender inequality in undergraduate ICT programs

1. Survey_Questions
2. Survey_allAnswers
3. Survey_Data_Analysis
4. Survey_Statistical_Analysis
5. Codebook of the Open Questions
 - 5.1 Survey_coding_question16
 - 5.2 Survey_coding_question19
 - 5.3 Survey_coding_question23
 - 5.4 Survey_coding_question24
 - 5.5 Survey_coding_question26
 - 5.6 Survey_coding_question28
 - 5.7 Survey_coding_question32
 - 5.8 Survey_coding_question33
 - 5.9 Survey_coding_question34
 - 5.10 Survey_coding_question35
 - 5.11 Survey_coding_question36
 - 5.12 Survey_coding_question37